

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D7.2 Project logo and website architecture

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Contact	Lisa Haller

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List of abbreviations

AE4EU	Agroecology for Europe
CDP	Communication and dissemination plan
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

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Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (IR) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This document gives an overview of the use of the ALL-Ready project logo as well as the architecture of the project website, including its structure and major features. It reflects the current status and the planned content that will be developed along with the progress of the project results during its lifespan. Possible modifications and improvements might be identified in future to address any needs not identified at this stage of the project.

In line with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.1), the website is one of the main communication tools used in ALL-Ready, giving general information on the project, its progress and outcomes. It is also the entry point for the knowledge center, providing access to the capacity building materials developed in WP5 as well as the Virtual Research Environment (VRE, cf. WP6).

1. Background

This document is a description of the ALL-Ready project logo and website, developed in the frame of WP7 Communication and Dissemination, led by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL Europe). It is strongly linked to the project's communication and dissemination plan (CDP, D7.2).

2. Logo

The project logo was designed by FiBL and was chosen by the consortium partners from three different proposed versions. It reflects agroecology and living labs, the dotted icon of the leaf symbolizes the rooted network of the living labs.

Figure 1. ALL-Ready project logo

The logo should be used on all communication and dissemination materials produced in the framework of the ALL-Ready project.

The project uses the below listed colours for highlighting and visual recognisability, also reflected in the logo.

Figure 2. ALL-Ready project colour scheme

3. ALL-Ready website

3.1 Objectives

The main aim of the project website is to provide information about the project to the general public and stakeholders. It is one of the main communication tools as set out in the CDP (D7.1) with the objectives to:

- provide relevant and up-to-date information on the project to a wide audience;
- ensure information is provided in an accessible and usable manner;
- promote the project's communication tools and its open results to increase public awareness;
- serve as an entry point for the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and provides access to the capacity building materials developed within the project;
- serve as a basis for the project's dissemination materials.

3.2 Hosting and access

The website has been created by FiBL using Typo3 and went online in April 2021. It is publicly accessible via:

<https://www.all-ready-project.eu/>

It is responsive, meaning that it adjusts its margins to the screen size or the web browser used. It can therefore be accessed and viewed easily on different devices including smartphones.

3.3 Updates and maintenance

The content of the website is updated on a regular basis by FiBL Europe during the course of the project period. All partners will be asked regularly to provide content and therefore help to keep the website up-to-date.

Specifically, news items, informing about the progress of the project, its latest results and deliverables, will be posted on the website regularly (home page and dedicated part in the section on communications). These news items are prepared by the project partners, following the template provided.

3.4 Structure of the website

The website is structured in four dedicated areas following a main menu:

1. About
2. Agroecology Living Labs & Research Infrastructures
3. Knowledge Center
4. Communication

All four main menu pages have sub-menus facilitating the navigation through the content in a structured way. In the following sections only the main menu pages will be illustrated and described.

All sub-pages consist of a main content section and a sidebar that gives the contact details to the respective responsible partners and/or key information on the project.

The language of the website is in English and no translation is foreseen.

3.4.1 Homepage

The “Homepage” page displays general information on the project and serves as entry point to more specific content (cf. Fig. 3 below).

The project logo is placed prominently on every subpage’s top left corner and stays fixed on the top of the page when scrolling down. The EU flag with project information is also fixed on the upper right corner of the page.

Figure 3. Main features on the homepage

This page is accessible via: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/>

3.4.2 About

The “About” page gives basic information about the background of project, its scope and approach. As shown in figure 4, it is structured in three main parts (cf. Fig 4):

1. An introduction explaining the environmental and societal issues that the project seeks to address;
2. The roadmap to be followed, establishing 3 main phases of the project;
3. Sub-menu to the detailed project description including, but not limited to, information about the project and its aims, the project consortium, the funding body as well as a short description of all WPs.

ABOUT AGROECOLOGY LIVING LABS & RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES KNOWLEDGE CENTER COMMUNICATIONS

All-Ready → About

About ALL-Ready

Today, agricultural systems are facing multiple challenges, including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality. Agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems and thus contribute to addressing these challenges. Based on the premise that Open Innovation Arrangements (OIAs) and in particular Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) are instruments that have large potential to contribute to amplifying agroecology in Europe, the main aim of ALL-Ready is to prepare a framework for a future European network of LLs and RIs (to be called "AgroEcoLLNet") that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. The project will lay the groundwork and prepare the necessary prerequisites and activities. Testing will verify and improve the project's outcomes, which will be communicated widely in Europe. The implementation plan will be tested and integrated into the validated framework of AgroEcoLLNet. The project relies on a highly participatory and inclusive approach and on experimentation in real life situations and thus itself uses a living lab approach. An underpinning principle of the project is strong stakeholder engagement, which has begun in the preparation of this proposal.

The project has 3 phases:

1. An initial preparatory phase in which the vision, scope and mission for the Network are defined and the criteria for inclusion in the Network of LLs and RIs as well as other forms of OIAs are defined. This will enable the mapping of current and emerging LLs, RIs and OIAs across Europe and their characteristics, highlighting best cases (WP1-WP2).
2. In a second phase, different prerequisites/ activities for the future Network will be prepared (sustainability, including funding, governance, capacity building, data and knowledge management). Plans for each of these will be constructed with stakeholders and then tested in a small-scale pilot network and then refined to match needs (WP3).
3. Finally, the outcomes of the work will be communicated widely throughout Europe by a variety of mechanisms. One of the final outcomes of the project will be a pilot-tested Implementation Plan for implementing the validated framework of AgroEcoLLNet, within Horizon Europe (WP4-WP7).

Objectives & aim >

Project Profile & approach >

Consortium & structure >

Work Packages >

Deliverables >

Funding >

ALL-Ready project

Funding: Horizon 2020

Call: Rural Renaissance - Fostering innovation and business opportunities

Topic: FNR-01-2020 - Strengthening the European agro-ecological research and innovation ecosystem

Grant agreement: No. 101000349

Coordinator: Dr Heather McKhann, INRAE, 147 rue de l'Université, 75338 Paris cedex 07, France

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ALL-Ready on Cordis

Contact
 Dr Heather McKhann
 Institut national de recherche en agriculture, alimentation et environnement INRAE, 147 rue de l'Université, 75338 Paris cedex 07, France
 Phone: +33 1 42 75 92 78
 e-mail: heather.mckhann@inrae.fr

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Print page Contact/Site info Privacy Policy Registry

Figure 4. About page

This page is accessible via: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/about.html>

Regarding the consortium structure, an integrated map giving an overview of the partners' locations was added. By clicking on the flag of each partner, website visitors can access the respective partner description, providing information on the organisation, their role in the project, a list of key people involved as well as contact details and links.

3.4.3 Agroecology living labs & research infrastructures

This page gives information on the key concepts, the vision and mission of ALL-Ready as well as the future partnership on Agroecological LLs and RIs and the pilot network developed in the course of ALL-Ready (cf. Fig. 5).

All-Ready >> Agroecology Living Labs & Research Infrastructures

Agroecology Living Labs & Research Infrastructures

This site gives information on the key concepts, the vision and mission of ALL-Ready as well as the future partnership on Agroecological LLs and RIs and the pilot network developed in the course of ALL-Ready.

VISION & MISSION >

PILOT NETWORK >

EUROPEAN R&I PARTNERSHIP >

Figure 5. Agroecology Living Labs & Research Infrastructures page

This page is accessible via: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/all-ri.html>

3.4.4 Knowledge Center

The “Knowledge Center” is the entry point for:

1. Capacity building and training materials developed in WP5
2. Virtual Research Environment established by WP6

Once available, the “Knowledge Hub” developed by the CSA AE4EU will also be linked in this section.

All-Ready >> Knowledge Center

Agroecology and living labs in publications

Agroecology

Living Labs

ALL-Ready will develop capacity training materials and a Virtual Research Environment. Here you will find the developed materials.

CAPACITY BUILDING AND TRAINING MATERIALS >

VIRTUAL RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT >

Contact

Miguel de Porras
 Address: Rue de la Presse 4, 1000 Brussels, Belgium
 Phone: +32 2 227 11 22
 E-Mail: [info.europe\(at\)fiabl.org](mailto:info.europe(at)fiabl.org)

www.fibl.org

Figure 6. Knowledge Center

This page is accessible via: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/knowledge-center.html>

3.4.5 Communications

The “Communications” section provides information on latest news or events, publications, research results, as well as access to the ALL-Ready social media channels. Each content is intended to disseminate the activities and findings related to the ALL-Ready project.

As described in the CDP (D7.1), ALL-Ready publications will be stored and published (after the embargo period) on ZENODO. With this ALL-Ready ensures that bibliographic metadata are included such as the funding body, the name of the action, acronym and grant number (already predefined in ZENODO), the publication date, and a persistent identifier. Via ZENODO, the publications are automatically stored on OpenAIRE, the European Union's electronic gateway for peer-reviewed articles and other important publications (www.openaire.eu). The website will link directly to the respective publications via the “publications” subpage.

Figure 7. Communications

This page is accessible via: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication.html>

3.4.5.1 News archiving

A feature for automatic news archiving is integrated in the website. News appear in the "News" section in the "Communications" section and feed into the news feed on the "Homepage". Additionally, they could also be made available by theme, e.g. pilot network.

3.4.5.2 Integration of social media accounts

Three social media accounts were created for the ALL-Ready project:

1. Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/ALL-Ready-104179844878249>
2. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/all-ready-eu>
3. Twitter: https://twitter.com/ALLReady_EU

In the “Communications” section the information regarding the social media accounts is summarized on a dedicated sub-page. Moreover, the links to the social media channels are integrated on the “Homepage” and the footer.

The social media posts contain information about the project and follow the social media strategy for ALL-Ready outlined in the CDP (D7.1).

3.4.6 Contact/Site Info

The “Contact/Site Info” page shows the project's contact addresses.

The contents of this website are owned by FiBL and protected by copyright law.

All legal requirements that must be followed (e.g. provision of information about the privacy policy, imprint information, etc.) have been taken into account during the creation of the website. The website uses SSL encryption to eliminate the transmission of personal data and protect all confidential content.

This page is available via: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/site-information.html>

4. Further development of the website

The sections above describe the current status and design of the ALL-Ready website. It will be continuously reviewed and will evolve during the project period reflecting the developments and outcomes of all WPs. At this stage, the following changes are foreseen:

- Once the project has further progressed, a structure targeting specific stakeholder groups will be considered. Content addressing the different groups could be displayed in these sections, accessed via the slider on the starting page;
- A newsletter subscription tool will be added on the starting page;
- With the progress of the project, project-related themes will be added to the news archive system to allow further categorization;
- Direct link to the registry of communication & dissemination activities (as described in D7.1) will be added in the Footer.
- The “Knowledge Hub” created in the CSA AE4EU will be linked in the section “Knowledge Center” to facilitate easy access to available materials of agroecology transition in the EU.